

**Impact-Related Proxies, Environmental Change, and
Faunal Extinctions across the Younger Dryas Boundary
in Hall's Cave, Texas:
Supporting Information**

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SEM and EDS

SI Fig S1. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) elemental map for a Fe-rich microspherule from Halls Cave (HC364; 151-153 cmbd). Note dendritic Fe-rich bleb on upper right and small embedded spherule.

SI Fig S2. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) elemental map energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) data for a Fe-rich microspherule from Halls Cave (HC364; 151-153 cmbd). See the elemental map in SI Fig S1.

MAP 1

SI Fig S3. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) elemental map for a Fe-rich microspherule from Halls Cave (HC364; 151-153 cmbd).

Acquisition Condition
 Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Current : ---
 Process Time : T4
 Live time : 220.93 sec.
 Real Time : 245.76 sec.
 DeadTime : 4.00 %
 Count Rate : 3099.00 CPS

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	38.66	61.46	0.07	146913	0.2669700	K
Na	4.21	4.66	0.06	17238	0.0166837	K
Mg	1.95	2.04	0.04	12615	0.0074999	K
Al	3.37	3.17	0.04	29342	0.0171128	K
Si	9.54	8.64	0.06	93626	0.0611235	K
S	1.01	0.80	0.02	10678	0.0084128	K
Ca	2.40	1.53	0.03	26405	0.0270597	K
Fe	38.86	17.70	0.11	167295	0.3893429	K
Total	100.00	100.00				

SI Fig S4. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) elemental map energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) data for a Fe-rich microspherule from Halls Cave (HC364; 151-153 cmbd). See the elemental map in SI Fig S3.

MAP 1

SI Fig S5. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) elemental map for a Fe-rich microspherule from Halls Cave (HC364; 151-153 cmbd).

SI Fig S6. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) elemental map energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) data for an Fe-rich microspherule from Halls Cave (HC364; 151-153 cmbd). See the elemental map in SI Fig S5.

MAP 1

SI Fig S7. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) elemental map for a Fe-rich microspherule from Halls Cave (HC364; 151-153 cmbd).

SI Fig S8. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) elemental map energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) data for a Fe-rich microspherule from Halls Cave (HC364; 151-153 cmbd). See the elemental map in SI Fig S7.

MAP 1

SI Fig S9. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) elemental map for an aluminosilicate microspherule from Halls Cave (HC364; 151-153 cmbd). Note multiple smaller spherules embedded in the larger spherule.

Acquisition Condition

Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Current : ---
 Process Time : T4
 Live time : 223.43 sec.
 Real Time : 245.76 sec.
 DeadTime : 4.00 %
 Count Rate : 2800.00 CPS

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
C	63.45	72.69	0.02	579417	0.2003136	K
O	27.25	23.44	0.04	182091	0.2137910	K
Na	0.54	0.32	0.01	19140	0.0119683	K
Mg	0.37	0.21	0.01	20063	0.0077066	K
Al	1.08	0.55	0.01	74233	0.0279721	K
Si	3.39	1.66	0.01	246376	0.1039222	K
Ca	1.68	0.58	0.01	103168	0.0683092	K
Fe	2.25	0.55	0.01	50313	0.0756542	K
Total	100.00	100.00				

SI Fig S10. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) elemental map energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) data for an aluminosilicate microspherule from Halls Cave (HC364; 151-153 cmbd). See the elemental map in SI Fig 9.

MAP 1

SI Fig S11. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) elemental map for a Fe-rich microspherule from Halls Cave (HC364; 151-153 cmbd). Note blebs of Na, Si, and Ca.

Acquisition Condition

Instrument : 6510 (LA)
 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Current : ---
 Process Time : T4
 Live time : 220.82 sec.
 Real Time : 245.76 sec.
 DeadTime : 9.00 %
 Count Rate : 3368.00 CPS

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
C	56.20	70.20	0.02	349062	0.1764149	K
O	25.70	24.10	0.05	145233	0.2492758	K
Na	0.92	0.60	0.01	19025	0.0173912	K
Al	0.50	0.28	0.01	21818	0.0120188	K
Si	0.89	0.47	0.01	42418	0.0261561	K
Ca	0.89	0.33	0.01	39665	0.0383932	K
Ti	0.29	0.09	0.01	8278	0.0105118	K
Fe	14.61	3.93	0.03	238459	0.5241755	K
Total	100.00	100.00				

SI Fig S12. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) elemental map energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) data for a Fe-rich microspherule from Halls Cave (HC364; 151-153 cmbd). See the elemental map in SI Fig 11.

MAP 1

SI Fig S13. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) elemental for a complex aluminosilicate microspherule from Halls Cave (HC364; 151-153 cmbd). Note multiple smaller spherules embedded in the larger spherule.

Acquisition Condition

Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Current : ---
 Process Time : T4
 Live time : 222.23 sec.
 Real Time : 245.76 sec.
 DeadTime : 6.00 %
 Count Rate : 2896.00 CPS

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
C	63.64	73.02	0.02	694105	0.2285288	K
O	27.41	23.61	0.04	213330	0.2385343	K
Mg	0.60	0.34	0.01	37019	0.0135420	K
Al	1.15	0.59	0.01	89480	0.0321108	K
Si	2.08	1.02	0.01	171151	0.0687521	K
Cl	0.20	0.08	0.00	15461	0.0082032	K
Ca	1.28	0.44	0.01	90296	0.0569375	K
Fe	3.63	0.90	0.01	93324	0.1336414	K
Total	100.00	100.00				

SI Fig S14. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) elemental map energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) data for a complex aluminosilicate microspherule from Halls Cave (HC364; 151-153 cmbd). See the elemental map in SI Fig 13.

MAP 1

SI Fig S15. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) elemental map for a complex aluminosilicate microspherule doublet from Halls Cave (HC364; 151-153 cmbd). Note Fe-rich dendritic crystals on the lower right spherule.

Supporting Information: Tables

SI Table S1. Radiocarbon ages used in the Bayesian age/depth model for Hall's Cave.

Lab #	RC (y BP)	RC ($\pm 1\sigma$)	depth (cm)	mid (cm)	Material dated	Reference	
1	41229-990	1460	100	005-010	7.5	Guano	Toomey 1993
2	CAMS-9193	1470	60	17.5	17.5	Bone	Bourne et al. 2016-1
3	41229-12115	1500	60	015-020	17.5	Gelatin	Cooke et al. 2003
4	CAMS-8728	2280	60	27.5	27.5	Bone	Bourne et al. 2016-1
5	41229-12118	2330	60	025-030	27.5	Gelatin	Cooke et al. 2003
6	CAMS-8738	2860	60	040-045	42.5	Bone	Bourne et al. 2016
7	41229-1119	2490	90	045-050	47.5	Charcoal	Toomey 1993
8	41229-12083	3190	70	51	51.0	Charcoal	Cooke et al. 2003
9	CAMS-8736	3250	60	050-055	52.5	Bone	Bourne et al. 2016
10	41229-6881	3190	90	055-060	57.5	Charcoal	Toomey 1993
11	41229-12117	4000	60	060-065	62.5	Gelatin	Cooke et al. 2003
12	CAMS-16024	4550	80	070-075	72.5	Bone	Bourne et al. 2016
13	41229-12099	5400	70	076-078	77.0	Humins	Cooke et al. 2003
14	CAMS-16022	4670	60	080-085	82.5	Bone	Bourne et al. 2016
15	41229-12162	5320	60	090-095	92.5	Gelatin	Cooke et al. 2003
16	41229-5265	4850	130	100	100.0	Charcoal	Toomey 1993
17	TX-1154	7940	130	100	100.0	Carbonate	Toomey 1993-1
18	CAMS-16029	6110	60	100-105	102.5	Bone	Bourne et al. 2016
19	41229-12164	7700	80	105-110	107.5	Gelatin	Cooke et al. 2003
20	Sun 2020-1	8820	30	116.5	116.5		Sun 2020
21	41229-12166	8630	60	120-125	122.5	Gelatin	Cooke et al. 2003
22	CAMS-16162	8730	60	130-135	132.5	Bone	Bourne et al. 2016
23	Sun 2020-2	9531	20	140.5	140.5		Sun 2020
24	41229-6882	7040	210	140-145	142.5	Bone	Toomey 1993
25	41229-12080	10310	70	145-150	142.5	Gelatin	Cooke et al. 2003
26	UCIAMS-71264	10190	25	147	147.0		This study
27	CAMS-8724	10340	70	145-150	147.5	Bone	Bourne et al. 2016
28	UCIAMS-71265	10195	25	150	150.0		This study
29	UCIAMS-250416	10110	25	149.0	151.0		This study
30	UCIAMS-250602	10270	30	150.0	151.0		This study
31	Sun 2020-3	11146	50	151.5	151.5		Sun 2020
32	UCIAMS-250603	10575	30	151.0	152.0		This study
33	UCIAMS-250417	10060	30	151.0	153.0		This study
34	UCIAMS-250604	10970	30	152.0	153.0		This study
35	41229-1360	7190	120	155-158	157.5	Carbonate	Toomey 1993
36	CAMS-33971	11290	60	155-160	157.5	Bone	Bourne et al. 2016
37	41229-12075	11310	60	155-160	157.5	Gelatin	Cooke et al. 2003
38	41229-12173	11410	70	165-170	167.5	Gelatin	Cooke et al. 2003
39	Sun 2020-4	11406	50	169.5	169.5		Sun 2020
40	Sun 2020-5	11406	50	171.5	171.5		Sun 2020
41	Sun 2020-6	11470	70	176.5	176.5		Sun 2020
42	CAMS-16018	11460	60	175-180	177.5	Bone	Bourne et al. 2016
43	41229-1326	11850	120	180	180.0	Carbonate	Toomey 1993
44	TX-6137	13050	140	180	180	Travertine	Toomey 1993-1
45	41229-N.D.	11550	70	185-190	187.5	Gelatin	Cooke et al. 2003
46	41229-1118	11770	150	190-195	192.5	Carbonate	Toomey 1993
47	41229-12176	12110	90	195-200	197.5	Gelatin	Cooke et al. 2003
48	CAMS-16016	12110	90	197.5	197.5	Bone	Bourne et al. 2016-1
49	41229-12177	14400	80	210-215	212.5	Gelatin	Cooke et al. 2003
50	CAMS-9196	12540	80	222.5	222.5	Bone	Bourne et al. 2016-1
51	41229-12073	12570	80	220-225	225.5	Gelatin	Cooke et al. 2003
52	CAMS-7197	12680	100	230-235	232.5	Bone	Bourne et al. 2016
53	41229-10879	15130	170	230-235	232.5	Bone	Toomey 1993
54	41229-12076	14700	90	235-240	237.5	Gelatin	Cooke et al. 2003
55	41229-12137	15290	90	260-260	260.0	Humic Acid	Cooke et al. 2003
56	41229-12179	13940	100	270-275	272.5	Gelatin	Cooke et al. 2003
57	41229-12180	16240	100	295-300	297.5	Gelatin	Cooke et al. 2003
58	41229-12181	16620	110	300-305	302.5	Gelatin	Cooke et al. 2003
59	41229-12183	16510	100	315-320	317.5	Gelatin	Cooke et al. 2003
60	41229-12131	16610	110	338-342	340.5	Humic Acid	Cooke et al. 2003
61	41229-12184	16770	100	345-350	347.5	Gelatin	Cooke et al. 2003

SI Table S2. Operating conditions for inductively coupled plasma-time of flight-mass spectrometer analysis (TOFWERK icpTOF R).

Instrument parameter	Value				
Plasma Power	1550 V				
Nebulizer Gas Flow	1.1-1.14 L/min				
Auxiliary Gas Flow	0.8 L/min				
Cooling Gas Flow	14 L/min				
Injector Diameter	2.5 mm				
Collision Cell Gas	5 mL/min He with 4.5% H ₂				
CCT Bias	-2.50 V				
Notch	Mass	29	32	36.3	41
	Amplitude (V)	1.6	2.0	2.0	1.2
Data acquisition	Continuous Mode				
Detected Mass Range	14-275 m/Z				
TOF Repetition Rate	33 kHz				
TOF Time Resolution	30 μs				
Integration Time	2 ms				
Sample Flow Rate	0.455 mL/min				
Transport Efficiency	6.6%				
(CeO/Ce)	< 3.0%				

SI Table S3. Elements were monitored for single particle-inductively coupled plasma-time of flight-mass spectrometer analysis and the corresponding particle mass and size detection limits.

Element	Isotope	Mass detection limit (g)	Size detection limit (nm, assuming pure metallic particle)	Size detection limit (nm, assuming pure metal oxide particle)	Metal oxide form
Al	²⁷ Al	6.90×10^{-15}	170	185	Al ₂ O ₃
Ti	⁴⁸ Ti	7.19×10^{-16}	67	82	TiO ₂
V	⁵¹ V	4.20×10^{-16}	51	75	V ₂ O ₅
Cr	⁵² Cr	3.27×10^{-16}	44	56	Cr ₂ O ₃
Mn	⁵⁵ Mn	2.48×10^{-16}	40	53	MnO ₂
Fe	⁵⁶ Fe	8.88×10^{-16}	60	77	Fe ₂ O ₃
Co	⁵⁹ Co	1.99×10^{-16}	35	44	Co ₃ O ₄
Ni	⁶⁰ Ni	8.64×10^{-16}	57	68	NiO
Cu	⁶⁵ Cu	6.66×10^{-16}	52	63	CuO

Zn	⁶⁶ Zn	1.50×10^{-15}	74	86	ZnO
As	⁷⁵ As	1.55×10^{-15}	80	101	As ₂ O ₃
Zr	⁹⁰ Zr	3.29×10^{-16}	46	53	ZrO ₂
Nb	⁹³ Nb	1.56×10^{-16}	33	44	Nb ₂ O ₅
Ru	¹⁰² Ru	4.16×10^{-16}	48	53	RuO ₂
Rh	¹⁰³ Rh	9.51×10^{-17}	30	35	Rh ₂ O ₃
Pd	¹⁰⁶ Pd	5.45×10^{-16}	67	59	PdO
Sn	¹²⁰ Sn	3.25×10^{-16}	44	48	SnO ₂
Sb	¹²¹ Sb	2.61×10^{-16}	42	49	Sb ₂ O ₃
Ba	¹³⁸ Ba	9.50×10^{-17}	37	33	BaO
La	¹³⁹ La	7.29×10^{-17}	28	29	La ₂ O ₃
Ce	¹⁴⁰ Ce	8.63×10^{-17}	29	30	CeO ₂
Pr	¹⁴¹ Pr	6.23×10^{-17}	26	28	Pr ₆ O ₁₁
Nd	¹⁴² Nd	1.70×10^{-16}	36	37	Nd ₂ O ₃
Sm	¹⁵² Sm	2.07×10^{-16}	38	38	Sm ₂ O ₃
Eu	¹⁵³ Eu	1.00×10^{-16}	33	31	Eu ₂ O ₃
Gd	¹⁵⁸ Gd	2.39×10^{-16}	39	41	Gd ₂ O ₃
Tb	¹⁵⁹ Tb	5.26×10^{-17}	23	25	Tb ₄ O ₇
Dy	¹⁶⁴ Dy	1.72×10^{-16}	34	36	Dy ₂ O ₃
Ho	¹⁶⁵ Ho	5.10×10^{-17}	22	24	Ho ₂ O ₃
Er	¹⁶⁶ Er	1.53×10^{-16}	32	34	Er ₂ O ₃
Tm	¹⁶⁹ Tm	5.15×10^{-17}	22	24	Tm ₂ O ₃
Yb	¹⁷⁴ Yb	1.57×10^{-16}	36	33	Yb ₂ O ₃
Lu	¹⁷⁵ Lu	4.38×10^{-17}	20	22	Lu ₂ O ₃
Hf	¹⁸⁰ Hf	1.95×10^{-16}	30	36	HfO ₂
Ta	¹⁸¹ Ta	1.78×10^{-16}	33	42	Ta ₂ O ₅
W	¹⁸⁴ W	3.55×10^{-16}	27	37	WO ₂
Re	¹⁸⁷ Re	1.04×10^{-16}	26	29	ReO ₂
Os	¹⁹² Os	1.20×10^{-16}	27	30	OsO ₂
Ir	¹⁹³ Ir	1.54×10^{-16}	25	32	IrO ₂
Pt	¹⁹⁵ Pt	4.09×10^{-16}	41	45	PtO ₂
Au	¹⁹⁷ Au	2.09×10^{-16}	28	34	Au ₂ O ₃
Pb	²⁰⁸ Pb	1.19×10^{-16}	27	30	PbO
Th	²³² Th	7.64×10^{-17}	23	26	ThO ₂
U	²³⁸ U	6.82×10^{-17}	19	24	UO ₂

The particle mass detection limit is calculated according to the Poisson distribution =

$$Mass_{detection\ limit} = 3.29\sqrt{background\ signal} + 2.71$$

The size detection limit is calculated as the equivalent spherical diameter from the particle mass detection limit, assuming pure metal and metal oxide phases.

SI Table S4. Bayesian age/depth analysis.

<https://zenodo.org/records/17475244>

SI Table S5 . Bayesian modeled sedimentation rates for Hall’s Cave.

<https://zenodo.org/records/17475244>

SI Table S6. Carbon and nitrogen stable isotopes and mercury (Hg) from bulk sediments at Hall’s Cave.

Sample ID	Depth (cm)	Depth (midpoint)	Sample Mass (mg)	Carbon			Nitrogen Content (mg)	Nitrogen Content (%)	Corrected $\delta^{15}\text{N}$	C/N Ratio	Hg (ng/g)	Hg/TOC
				Content (mg)	Carbon Content (%)	Corrected $\delta^{13}\text{C}$						
HC349	10-20	15	46.50	0.86	1.84	-22.16	0.08	0.17	6.98	10.93	20.72	11.23
HC351	105-109	107	44.04	0.29	0.66	-21.82	0.04	0.09	8.60	7.62	15.36	23.23
HC353	129-131	130	44.29	0.27	0.62	-21.61	0.04	0.09	9.89	7.21	19.55	31.67
HC355	133-135	134	44.61	0.58	1.30	-22.55	0.05	0.12	9.21	11.23	16.12	12.41
HC357	137-139	138	45.28	0.22	0.50	-22.31	0.03	0.07	8.95	7.28	18.58	37.40
HC359	141-143	142	46.56	0.30	0.65	-22.47	0.04	0.08	9.04	8.22	17.30	26.63
HC361	145-147	146	43.24	0.59	1.37	-22.76	0.05	0.11	8.04	12.33	17.09	12.45
HC362	147-149	146	43.28	0.48	1.12	-22.87	0.04	0.10	8.61	11.49	15.91	14.26
HC363	149-151	150	45.12	0.31	0.69	-22.52	0.03	0.06	7.80	10.67	17.14	24.89
HC364	151-153	152	44.03	0.22	0.49	-21.71	0.02	0.05	9.29	9.42	14.28	28.84
HC365	153-155	154	40.01	0.26	0.65	-21.61	0.03	0.07	10.57	8.85	14.22	21.85
HC366	155-157	156	40.16	0.26	0.65	-21.64	0.03	0.08	11.33	8.17	15.80	24.29
HC368	159-161	160	49.14	0.22	0.44	-20.41	0.03	0.06	11.18	7.74	15.50	35.38
HC370	163-165	164	44.02	0.31	0.71	-21.43	0.04	0.08	11.12	8.60	16.10	22.60
HC372	170-175	172.5	43.05	0.20	0.46	-21.30	0.03	0.06	10.71	7.61	15.15	33.18
HC373	180-182	181	44.08	0.18	0.41	-21.11	0.02	0.05	10.58	8.44	12.00	29.39

USGS 40 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ Standard Deviation
 USGS 40 $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ Standard Deviation
 USGS 41a $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ Standard Deviation

SI Table S7. Mass corrected magnetic susceptibility ($10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1}$).

Sample	Top cm (bd)	Bottom cm (bd)	MidPt cm (bd)	<i>K</i> lf SI units	<i>Kh</i> f SI units	<i>Vol_K</i> fd %	Wt (g)	<i>X</i> lf $10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1}$
HC353	129	131	130	102.8	94.6	7.9	8.011	0.90
HC355	133	155	134	99.2	90.4	8.8	8.046	0.86
HC356	137	139	138	97.9	90.2	7.9	7.841	0.87
HC359	141	143	142	95.0	87.6	7.8	7.882	0.84
HC361	145	147	146	91.6	85.0	7.1	7.408	0.86
HC362	147	149	148	102.0	94.6	7.3	7.879	0.91
HC363	149	151	150	99.1	91.8	7.4	7.498	0.92
HC364	151	153	152	119.8	111.6	6.9	8.535	0.98
HC365	153	155	154	106.0	98.2	7.3	8.091	0.92
HV366	155	157	156	118.3	109.4	7.5	8.760	0.94
HC368	159	161	160	99.2	91.8	7.5	7.935	0.87
HC370	163	165	164	95.3	88.1	7.6	7.695	0.87
HC372	170	175	173	98.6	91.6	7.1	7.440	0.93

SI Table S8. Hall's Cave data on aciniform carbon (soot), nanodiamonds, carbon spherules, magnetic spherules, and shocked quartz (number per 2000 grains).

Sample	Depth range	Depth (mid)	Soot (ppm)	Nanodiamonds (ppb)	CS/kg	MSp/kg	Sh. Qtz (#/2000)
HC349	10-20	15	0	4	0	0	0
HC351	105-109	107	0	1	--	--	0
HC352	127-129	128	0	1	0	0	--
HC353	129-131	130	0	11	--	--	0
HC354	131-133	132	0	15	0	0	--
HC355	133-135	134	0	0	--	--	0
HC356	135-137	136	0	23	0	0	--
HC357	137-139	138	0	23	--	--	0
HC358	139-141	140	0	7	0	0	--
HC359	141-143	142	0	4	0	0	--
HC360	143-145	144	0	23	3	0	0
HC361	145-147	146	0	12	0	0	0
HC362	147-149	148	0	1	0	0	0
HC363	149-151	150	0	1	12	112	1
HC364	151-153	152	2400	105	9	370	5
HC365	153-155	154	400	61	3	0	0
HC366	155-157	156	0	0	0	0	1
HC367	157-159	158	0	0	0	0	0
HC368	159-161	160	0	0	--	--	--
HC369	161-163	162	0	0	0	0	0
HC370	163-165	164	0	0	--	--	--
HC372	170-175	172.5	0	1	0	0	0

SI Table S9. Hall's Cave data on nanodiamond polytypes.

n-diamond

hkl	d-spacing	g-spacing
111	2.0600	0.485
200	1.7800	0.562
220	1.2600	0.794
311	1.0700	0.935
222	1.0400	0.962
400	0.8980	1.114
331	0.8180	1.222
420	0.7960	1.256
422	0.7260	1.377
511	0.6830	1.464

cubic diamond

hkl	d-spacing	g-spacing
111	2.0593	0.486
220	1.2611	0.793
311	1.0754	0.930
400	0.8917	1.121
331	0.8183	1.222
422	0.7281	1.373
511	0.6864	1.457
333	0.6864	1.457

p-diamond

hkl	d-spacing	g-spacing
111	2.0800	0.481
221	1.2200	0.820
222	1.0400	0.962
412	0.7900	1.266
413	0.7100	1.408
333	0.6900	1.449
334(?)	0.6100	1.639
703	0.5900	1.695

i-carbon

hkl	d-spacing	g-spacing
110	3.0367	0.329
111	2.5300	0.395
200	2.1233	0.471
211	1.8067	0.554
220	1.5367	0.651
311	1.2967	0.771
400	1.0967	0.912
422	0.9093	1.100
431	0.8390	1.192

hex diamond

hkl	d-spacing	g-spacing
100	2.1840	0.458
2	2.0590	0.486
101	1.9300	0.518
102	1.4980	0.667
110	1.2610	0.793
103	1.1620	0.86
200	1.0920	0.916
112	1.0750	0.93
201	1.0560	0.947
202	0.9650	1.036
203	0.8550	1.17
210	0.8260	1.211
211	0.8090	1.235
105	0.7710	1.297
212	0.7660	1.305
300	0.7280	1.373
213	0.7070	1.413
302	0.6860	1.457
205	0.6580	1.521
106	0.6550	1.527

SI Table S10. SP-ICP-TOF-MS data for Hall's Cave.

<https://zenodo.org/records/17475244>

SI Table S11. Osmium isotopes and PGE data from Sun et al. 2020¹. Note large peak in Pt shown in this table (red text) was omitted from the Sun et al. published data as shown in a recent publication by Young 2025².

Sample	Depth_cm	Weight_g	¹⁸⁷ Os/ ¹⁸⁸ Os	Os_ppt	Ir_ppt	Ru_ppt	Pt_ppt	Pd_ppt	Re_ppt	Pt/Pd
HC16_22	133	1.08	1.79	33.98	23.9	12.86	113.3	101.1	1475	1.12
HC16_21	135	1.11	2.09	29.54	4.8	4.2	136.3	140.1	1098	0.97
HC16_20	137	1.04	1.5	44.6	11.1	24.98	180	46.1	1099	3.90
HC16_19	139	1.1	0.28	259.9	2.2	14.6	275.5	41.1	1039	6.70
HC16_18	141	1.02	1.96	32.5	10.7	10.2	185.7	158.9	1174	1.17
HC16_17	143	1.06	1.11	56.9	13.1	17.87	965.6	33.2	1251	29.08
HC16_16	145	1.07	2.02	31.29	9.2	16.47	237.2	112	1205	2.12
HC16_15	147	1.12	2.1	29.14	3.9	7.76	128.1	140.9	1013	0.91
HC16_14	149	1.13	1.8	31.8	8.2	2.11	78.1	72.5	1121	1.08
HC16_01	151	1.06	2.07	22.63	15.96	8.58	136.4	26.674	1057	5.11
HC16_02	153	1.09	1.96	24.64	22.8	10.45	1807	31.312	1099	57.71
HC16_03	155	1	0.15	829.7	22.7	5.09	124.7	44.84	1151	2.78
HC16_04	157	1.06	1.55	34.13	13.1	31.36	176.9	53.25	1035	3.32
HC16_05	159	1.02	2.06	23.7	11.4	15.17	151.7	66.84	905	2.27
HC16_06	161	1.01	2.03	24.3	8.3	14	124.9	117.2	970	1.07
HC16_07	163	1.03	1.75	28.4	8.5	15.1	132.5	193.2	964	0.69
HC16_08	165	1.1	2.1	23.8	3.8	3.8	53.8	257.8	989	0.21
HC16_09	167	1.1	2.07	25.2	15.5	31.63	136.6	72.2	1030	1.89
HC16_10	169	1.13	0.42	127.1	18.9	7.78	171.6	175	1115	0.98
HC16_11	171	1.09	1.48	30.2	12	9.36	321.8	90.4	976	3.56
HC16_12	173	1.1	2.06	21.7	17.3	18.87	127.3	50	1025	2.55
HC16_13	175	1.08	1.9	26.9	12.1	12.3	134.8	234.7	973	0.57

SI Table S12. ET comparative data
<https://zenodo.org/records/17475244>

Bayesian code

Hall's Cave P_Sequence

Options()

```
{
Curve="IntCal20";
BCAD=FALSE;
kIterations=60;
};
```

Plot()

```

{
Sequence("Halls Cave, TX")
{
Outlier_Model("General", T(5), U(0,4),"t");
P_Sequence("Halls Cave",0.5,5)
{
Boundary(){z=347.5;};

R_Date("41229-12184",16770,100){z=347.5;Outlier(1);};
R_Date("41229-12131",16610,110){z=340.5;Outlier(1);};
R_Date("41229-12183",16510,100){z=317.5;Outlier(1);};
    R_Date("41229-12181",16620,110){z=302.5;Outlier();color="orange";};
R_Date("41229-12180",16240,100){z=297.5;Outlier(1);};
    R_Date("41229-12179",13940,100){z=272.5;Outlier();color="orange";};
R_Date("41229-12137",15290,90){z=260.0;Outlier(1);};
    R_Date("41229-12076",14700,90){z=237.5;Outlier();color="orange";};
    R_Date("41229-10879",15130,170){z=232.5;Outlier();color="orange";};
R_Date("CAMS-7197",12680,100){z=232.5;Outlier(1);};
R_Date("41229-12073",12570,80){z=225.5;Outlier(1);};
R_Date("CAMS-9196",12540,80){z=222.5;Outlier(1);};
    R_Date("41229-12177",14400,80){z=212.5;Outlier();color="orange";};

    Boundary(Bolling-Allerod){z=211.0;};

R_Date("41229-12176",12110,90){z=197.51;Outlier(1);};
R_Date("CAMS-16016",12110,90){z=197.5;Outlier(1);};
R_Date("41229-1118",11770,150){z=192.5;Outlier(1);};

```

R_Date("41229-N.D.",11550,70){z=187.5;Outlier(1)};;
 R_Date("TX-6137",13050,140){z=180.01;Outlier();color="orange"};;
 R_Date("41229-1326",11850,120){z=180.0;Outlier();color="orange"};;
R_Date("CAMS-16018",11460,60){z=177.5;Outlier(1)};;
R_Date("Sun 2020-6",11470,70){z=176;Outlier(1)};;
R_Date("Sun 2020-5",11406,50){z=171;Outlier(1)};;
R_Date("Sun 2020-4",11406,50){z=169;Outlier(1)};;
R_Date("41229-12173",11410,70){z=167.5;Outlier(1)};;
R_Date("41229-12075",11310,60){z=157.52;Outlier(1)};;
R_Date("CAMS-33971",11290,60){z=157.51;Outlier(1)};;
 R_Date("41229-1360",7190,120){z=157.5;Outlier();color="orange"};;
 R_Date("UCIAMS-250417",10060,30){z=153.01;Outlier();color="orange"};;
R_Date("UCIAMS-250604",10970,30){z=153.0;Outlier(1)};;

 Boundary(Lower YD){z=152.5};

R_Date("UCIAMS-250603",10575,30){z=152.0;Outlier(1)};;
R_Date("UCIAMS-250602",10270,30){z=151.02;Outlier(1)};;
R_Date("UCIAMS-250416",10110,25){z=151.01;Outlier(1)};;
 R_Date("Sun 2020-3",11146,50){z=151.0;Outlier();color="orange"};;
R_Date("UCIAMS-71265",10195,25){z=150.01;Outlier(1)};;
 R_Date("CAMS-8724",10340,70){z=147.5;Outlier();color="orange"};;
R_Date("UCIAMS-71264",10190,25){z=147.0;Outlier(1)};;

 Boundary(YD/Holocene){z=145.0};

 R_Date("41229-12080",10310,70){z=142.51;Outlier();color="orange"};;

```
R_Date("41229-6882",7040,210){z=142.5;Outlier();color="orange";};
R_Date("Sun 2020-2",9531,20){z=140;Outlier(1);};
R_Date("CAMS-16162",8730,60){z=132.5;Outlier();color="orange";};
R_Date("41229-12166",8630,60){z=122.5;Outlier(1);};
R_Date("Sun 2020-1",8820,30){z=116;Outlier(1);};
R_Date("41229-12164",7700,80){z=107.5;Outlier(1);};
R_Date("CAMS-16029",6110,60){z=102.5;Outlier(1);};
R_Date("TX-1154",7940,130){z=100.01;Outlier();color="orange";};
R_Date("41229-5265",4850,130){z=100.0;Outlier();color="orange";};
R_Date("41229-12162",5320,60){z=92.5;Outlier(1);};
R_Date("CAMS-16022",4670,60){z=82.5;Outlier(1);};
R_Date("41229-12099",5400,70){z=77.0;Outlier();color="orange";};
R_Date("CAMS-16024",4550,80){z=72.5;Outlier(1);};
R_Date("41229-12117",4000,60){z=62.5;Outlier(1);};
R_Date("41229-6881",3190,90){z=57.5;Outlier(1);};
R_Date("CAMS-8736",3250,60){z=52.5;Outlier(1);};
R_Date("41229-12083",3190,70){z=51.0;Outlier(1);};
R_Date("41229-1119",2490,90){z=47.5;Outlier(1);};
R_Date("CAMS-8738",2860,60){z=42.5;Outlier(1);};
R_Date("41229-12118",2330,60){z=27.51;Outlier(1);};
R_Date("CAMS-8728",2280,60){z=27.5;Outlier(1);};
R_Date("41229-12115",1500,60){z=17.5;Outlier(1);};
R_Date("CAMS-9193",1470,60){z=17.5;Outlier(1);};
R_Date("41229-990",1460,100){z=7.5;Outlier(1);};

Boundary(){z=7.5;};

};
```

};

};

References

- 1 Sun, N., Brandon, A., Forman, S., Waters, M. & Befus, K. Volcanic origin for Younger Dryas geochemical anomalies ca. 12,900 cal BP. *Science advances* **6**, eaax8587 (2020).
- 2 Young, M. D. Geochemical re-evaluation supports cosmic impact rather than volcanism at Younger Dryas onset, Hall's Cave, Texas: Reply to Sun et al. 2020. *Airbursts and Cratering Impacts* **3**, 20250007 (2025).